

STUDY OF SYNTHESIS AND CHARACTERISTIC OF THE PRECURSOR OF SiC CERAMIC POLYSILANES CONTAINING ACTIVE FUNCTION GROUP

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ABSTRACT

Four kinds of polysilanes containing Si-H bond, $\{-(\text{CH}_3)_2\text{SiCH}_3\}_x-(\text{CH}_3\text{SiH})_y\}_n$, $\{-(\text{PhSiPh})_x-(\text{CH}_3\text{SiH})_y-(\text{CH}_3)_2\text{SiCH}_3\}_z\}_n$ and $\{-(\text{CH}_3)_2\text{SiCH}_3\}_x-(\text{CH}_3\text{SiH})_y-(\text{CH}_2=\text{CHSiCH}_3)_z\}_n$, have been synthesized. The structures of these copolymers were investigated by IR, $^1\text{H-NMR}$ and $^{13}\text{C-NMR}$ and their molecular weights were measured.

Keywords: Methylchlorosilane, Methylvinylchlorosilane, dimethylchlorosilane, diphenylchlorosilane

Generally, the application of polysilanes includes, 1. As precursors to silicon carbide ceramics; 2. As photoinitiators in radical reactions; 3. As photoconductive materials and 4. As photoresists in microelectronics^[1]. Among these, the application as precursors to SiC ceramics is the most. Si-H bond in polysilanes is a latent function and may improve cross-linking of the polymer, therefore, polysilane containing Si-H bond, such as $-(\text{H}_2\text{SiCH}_3)_n-$, gives an 85% SiC ceramic yield^[2]. However, some linear polymers, such as $-(\text{CH}_3)_2\text{SiCH}_3)_n-$, give negligible ceramic yields because of reversion reactions leading to volatile molecules during pyrolysis^[3].

Table 1. The results of copolymerization of a few kinds of organodichlorosilanes

Monomers	Mole ratio of monomers	sodium (mole)	Reaction time (hs)	Yield (%)	Appearance of product	Melting range (°C)	Solubility	\bar{M}_n
$(\text{CH}_3)_2\text{SiCl}_2^a / \text{CH}_3\text{SiHCl}_2$	0.415/ 0.483	1.52	3	92.0	white-viscous-liquid	liquid	soluble	185-307
				5.1	white-solid	infusible at 300°C	insoluble	/
$(\text{CH}_3)_2\text{SiCl}_2^a / \text{Ph}_2\text{SiCl}_2$	0.365/ 0.360	1.31	3	91.8	white-viscous-liquid	liquid	soluble	458-2100
				5.5	white-solid	infusible at 300°C	insoluble	/
$\text{Ph}_2\text{SiCl}_2^a / \text{CH}_3\text{SiHCl}_2$	0.241/ 0.435	1.65	2	91.2	white-viscous-liquid	liquid	soluble	174-251
				5.7	white-solid	infusible at 300°C	insoluble	/
$\text{Ph}_2\text{SiCl}_2^a / \text{CH}_3\text{SiHCl}_2 / (\text{CH}_3)_2\text{SiCl}_2$	0.154/ 0.435/ 0.232	1.74	2	90.7	white-viscous-liquid	liquid	soluble	217-6399
				7.6	white-solid	infusible at 300°C	insoluble	/
$\text{V}_1\text{SiCH}_3\text{Cl}_2^b / (\text{CH}_3)_2\text{SiCl}_2 / \text{CH}_3\text{SiHCl}_2$	0.300/ 0.300/ 0.400	2.3	20	99.5	white-solid	infusible at 300°C	insoluble	/

a. Solvent, dimethylbenzene, 300ml. Reaction temperature, 135-140°C.

b. Solvent, THF, 600ml. Reaction temperature, 67°C.

In this paper, three kinds of polysilanes containing Si-H bond, copolymer of dimethyldichlorosilane and methyldichlorosilane (CODMSMS), copolymer of diphenyldichlorosilane and methyldichlorosilane (CODPSMS), copolymer of diphenyldichlorosilane and methyldichlorosilane and dimethyldichlorosilane (CODPSMSDMS), and copolymer of methylvinyedichlorosilane and dimethyldichlorosilane and methyldichlorosilane (COMVSDMSMS), have been synthesized. Main results are listed in Table 1. The experiment shows, 1. Though the reaction time is short (except COMVSDMSMS), the yield of soluble copolymers is very high (above 90%); 2. Every kind of product can be separated into two ingredients, and the former is soluble and white and viscous liquid while the latter is insoluble and infusible solid (except COMVSDMSMS).

Infrared spectra of these Polysilanes (Figure 1) show, 1. Because there are strong peaks at 800cm^{-1} (a-f) and 490cm^{-1} (c, d, e and f), the products are copolymers^[4]; 2. The peaks at 2900cm^{-1} (a-f) are absorption bands of $-\text{CH}_3$ and the peaks at 3030cm^{-1} (c, d, e and f) are absorption band of phenyl group. $^1\text{H-NMR}$ of the copolymers (Figure 2, 4, 5) shows that there are peaks at about 3.70ppm and 0.2ppm in all of the spectra and peaks at about 7.0ppm (Figure 4 and 5). 3.70ppm is resonance peak of $\text{Si-H}^{[1]}$ and 7.0ppm is resonance peak of phenyl group and 0.2ppm is that of $-\text{CH}$. $^{13}\text{C-NMR}$ of CODPSMS shows the presence of phenyl group at about 130ppm. According to the results of IR and NMR, the structure of these copolymers are $\{ \text{-(CH}_3\text{SiCH}_3\text{)}_x\text{-(CH}_3\text{SiH)}_y\}_n$, $\{ \text{-(PhSiPh)}_x\text{-(CH}_3\text{SiH)}_y\}_n$ and $\{ \text{-(PhSiPh)}_x\text{-(CH}_3\text{SiH)}_y\text{-(CH}_3\text{SiCH}_3\text{)}_z\}_n$.

The IR and $^1\text{H-NMR}$ of COMVSDMSMS do not be showed in this paper, but our experiments have showed that a part of Si-H can react with $\text{CH}_2=\text{CH}-$ and the absorption bands of $\text{CH}_2=\text{CH}-$ become weak but the peaks of Si-H still are strong. As a comparison, the result of copolymerization of $(\text{CH}_3)_2\text{SiCl}_2$ and Ph_2SiCl_2 is also listed but does not show the figures of IR and $^1\text{H-NMR}$.

Figure 1. IR Spectra of polysilanes, a, b; CODMSMS; c, d; CODPSMS; e, f; CODPSMSDMS; a, c and e are soluble liquid while b, d and f are insoluble and infusible solid.

Figure 4. $^1\text{H-NMR}$ Spectrum of soluble CODPSMS.

Figure 2. $^1\text{H-NMR}$ Spectrum of soluble CODMSMS.

Figure 3. $^{13}\text{C-NMR}$ Spectrum of soluble CODPSMS.

Figure 5. $^1\text{H-NMR}$ spectrum of soluble CODPSMSDMS.

References

1. West R. , Jim Maxka; *Inorganic and Organometallic Polymers*, American Chemistry Society, 1988, 6.
2. Bruno B. , Robert J. P. Corriu, Dominique L. , Mutin P. H. , Jean-Mard P. , Andre V. ; *Organometallics*, 1991, 5(10), 1457.
3. Wynne K. J. , Rice R. W. ; *Rev. Mater. Sci.* , 1984, 4, 297.
4. Zhang Zhiyi, Lu Yi, Tan Zilie; *J. of National University of Defense Technology*, 1991, 1(13), 69.